

Disrupting Noxious Synergies of Indoor Air Pollutants and their Impact in Childhood Health and Wellbeing using Advanced Intelligent Multi-sensing and Green Interventions

Communication and Dissemination Materials

Deliverable number	7.1
Due date	31/12/2022
Nature	DEC
Dissemination level	Public
Work Package	7
Lead Beneficiary	EFA
Contributing Beneficiaries	INLE, NKUA

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Project and Document Information

Grant Agreement No	101057271	Acronym	SynAir-G
Project Full Title	Disrupting Noxious Synergies of Indoor Air Pollutants and their Impact in Childhood Health and Wellbeing using Advanced Intelligent Multi-sensing and Green Interventions		
Call	HORIZON-HLTH-2021-ENVHLTH-02		
Topic	HORIZON-HLTH-2021-ENVHLTH-02-02	Type of action	RIA

Disrupting Noxious Synergies of Indoor Air Pollutants and their Impact in Childhood Health and Wellbeing using Advanced Intelligent Multi-sensing and Green Interventions

Coordinator	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens		
Start Date	01/09/2022	Duration	48 months
Deliverable	D7.1	Work Package	WP7
Document Type	DEC	Dissemination Level	Public
Lead beneficiary	European Federation of Allergy and Airways Diseases Patients' Associations (EFA)		
Responsible author	Valeria Ramiconi, EFA		
Contractual due date	31/12/2022	Actual submission date	29/12/2022

Contributor Information

Deliverable Contributors	
Contributor Name	Organisation (Acronym)
Valeria Ramiconi	European Federation of Allergy and Airways Diseases Patients' Associations (EFA)
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Maria Kampa	INLECOM Group (INLE)
Nikos Papadopoulos	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA)

Overview

EFA completed deliverable 7.1, 'Communication and Dissemination Materials,' for Work Package 7, 'Data Management, Guidelines, Dissemination and Exploitation.' The public deliverable includes the project website, social media channels, project logo, and other branding materials.

Digital Material

Website

The SynAir-G project website was launched in November 2022 (D7.12 Website Launch) with ongoing updates throughout December.

The website construction followed the guidance of the website briefing, detailed in the D7.12 deliverable submission, developed by partner EFA and reviewed by partner INLE with final approval by coordinator NKUA.

The target audiences of the website are researchers, healthcare professionals, policy-makers, patients and civil society at large. Therefore, we wanted to keep the structure "user-friendly", using a lay language without compromising the scientific rigor. We gave emphasis to the news and publications sections, adding also subsections explaining the scientific research and method behind the project, and background information on Indoor air quality, asthma and allergy.

The website was built with WordPress and hosted on EFA's OVHcloud account. It will use Google Analytics or a relevant plugin to evaluate website metrics. Website analytics will be shared regularly in the periodic report and reviews.

EFA will evaluate website efficacy towards dissemination and communication aims using the following metrics. These metrics will be evaluated for periodic reporting:

- Website traffic
- Pageviews per session
- Session duration
- Top traffic sources
- Top pages

Social Media

EFA established two social media pages for the project, on Twitter and LinkedIn.

The twitter page, @SynAir_G is adorned with the project logo, social media banner and a funding disclosure statement. It features 19 followers and 8 posts. Posts have an average engagement rate of 10.2% for the period of 01/09/22-21/12/22, as detailed in the table below.

SynAir-G Twitter Analytics 01/09/22-21/12/22			
Post	Impressions	Engagement	Engagement Rate (%)
Welcome to SynAir-G	288	40	13.9
Cluster KoM	320	37	11.6
Close Cluster KoM	112	8	7.1
Retweet of EFA Patients	N/A	N/A	N/A

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Quote Tweet of Irene Norstedt	95	13	13.7
Project KoM	311	42	13.5
EFA Partner Spotlight	74	7	9.5
NKUA gets approval	680	15	2.2
Total	1880	162	10.2

The LinkedIn page is an organisation page, @SynAir-G, featuring the project logo, social media banner and a funding disclosure statement. It features 45 followers and 2 posts. Posts boast an average engagement rate of 15.6% for the period of 01/09/22-21/12/22, as detailed in the table below.

SynAir-G LinkedIn Analytics 01/09/22-21/12/22			
Post	Impressions	Engagement	Engagement Rate (%)
Welcome to SynAir-G	902	171	19
Cluster Post	221	27	12.2
Total	1123	198	15.6

A comprehensive social media plan will be detailed in D7.2, “Dissemination and Communication Plan,” to be submitted M6.

Analytics will be evaluated for periodic reporting.

Logo

EFA completed the project logo, featured to the left, on 06/10/2022 with input and quality control from project coordinator Nikos Papadopoulos, NKUA.

The fonts and colour palette used are available in the Annex 1.

Version History				
Version	Date	%	Changes	Author
0.1	29/09/2022	25	Selection of logo design from three proposals	EFA
0.2	05/10/2022	50	Colour palette proposals for selected logo	EFA
0.3	05/10/2022	90	Font changes	EFA
1.0	6/10/2022	100	Final version ready for use	EFA

Quality Control (includes peer & quality reviewing)			
Date	Version	Name (Organisation)	Role & Scope
29/09/2022	0.1	Nikos Papadopoulos, NKUA	Selection and comments on colour palette
05/10/2022	0.2	Nikos Papadopoulos, NKUA	Comments on colour palette proposals

Branding Materials

Visual Identity Guidelines

EFA developed visual identity guidelines for the project on 27/10/2022. They were derived from ongoing consultation and quality control with project coordinator Nikos Papadopoulos, NKUA. For version history and quality control processes, please reference the tables detailing logo development.

Complete visual identity guidelines for the project are attached as Annex 1.

Deliverable Submission Form

EFA prepared the project's deliverable submission form by 01/11/2022. It was authored and reviewed by EFA and by WP7 leader, Maria Kampa, INLE.

It is available as Annex 2.

Version History				
Version	Date	%	Changes	Author
0.1	27/10/2022	75	Format and design proposed	EFA
0.2	01/11/2022	90	Addition of tables for project and document information and authoring, revision, and Q&A information	INLE
1	02/11/2022	100	Style settings, Final version ready for use	EFA

Quality Control (includes peer & quality reviewing)			
Date	Version	Name (Organisation)	Role & Scope
01/11/2022	0.2	Maria Kampa, INLE	General review

Roll-up Banner

EFA created a promotional roll-up banner for meetings, events and other promotional opportunities. The final design was completed on 20/12/2022 with input and quality control from project coordinator Nikos Papadopoulos, NKUA, and WP7 lead Maria Kampa, INLE. Roll-up banner is available as Appendix 1.

Version History				
Version	Date	%	Changes	Author
0.1	06/12/2022	25	First visual elements proposal	EFA
0.2	13/12/2022	50	Content and design edits	EFA
0.3	15/12/2022	80	Design edits	EFA
0.4	20/12/2022	90	Final design edits	EFA
1.0	20/12/2022	100	Final version ready for use	EFA

Quality Control (includes peer & quality reviewing)			
Date	Version	Name (Organisation)	Role & Scope
16/12/2022	0.3	Nikos Papadopoulos, NKUA	Content and design review
20/12/2022	0.3	Maria Kampa, INLE	Content and design review

Social Media Banners

EFA developed social media banners for project social media pages. This was done with internal quality control only, as visual identity guidelines and other materials were well developed and provided a basis for autonomous work.

Social media banners can be found in Appendix 2.

Version History				
Version	Date	%	Changes	Author
0.1	15/12/2022	25	Four banner proposals	EFA
.02	15/12/2022	50	Design choice with content edits	EFA
1	20/12/2022	100	Final version ready for use	EFA

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Poster

For practical reasons, poster development has been postponed. Posters will be designed as needed with respect to other WP and task timelines. We foresee the use of posters as educational material in schools, for the presentation of research at conferences or to disseminate guidelines coming out of the project. Given that the content, including possible translation services, and designs will need to be adapted to each task, posters will be developed as project materials become available.

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Appendix 1

Roll-up Banner

 Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No 101057271. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Appendix 2

Twitter Banner

LinkedIn Banner

SynAir-G

Logo Guidelines

Versions

SynAir-G

Horizontal

Icon

Large

Small

SynAir-G

SynAir-G

Colors

C 70 **M** 17
R 58 **G** 168 **B** 223
3aa8df

C 59 **M** 6
R 99 **G** 191 **B** 237
63bfed

C 91 **M** 58
R 9 **G** 99 **B** 174
0963ae

M 37 **Y** 80
R 248 **V** 174 **B** 64
f8ae40

M 51 **Y** 97
R 242 **G** 144 **B** 5

Font

Montserrat Black

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

1234567890

Montserrat Regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

1234567890

f29005

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Lead beneficiary	[Organisation (ACRONYM)]		
Responsible author	[Name (Organisation acronym)]		
Contractual due date	[dd/mm/yyyy]	Actual submission date	[dd/mm/yyyy]

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Authoring, Revision & QA Information

Deliverable Contributors	
Contributor Name	Organisation (Acronym)

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Version	Date	%	Changes	Author

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Date	Version	Name (Organisation)	Role & Scope

